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E-mail: editor@iaeme.com, iaemedu@gmail.com Website: www.iaeme.com Mobile: +91-9884798314

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PHYCOREMEDIATION OF SERVO BOAT ENGINE OIL - HISTOCHEMICAL STUDIES

Josmin Laali Nisha LL¹ Poonguzhali T.V²

Research scholar, P.G and Research Department of Botany, Queen Mary's College,
Chennai-600 004, India.

Associate Professor, P.G and Research Department of Botany, Queen Mary's College,
Chennai-600 004, India.

ABSTRACT

Algae, with their inherent ability to absorb pollutants from aquatic environments, present a promising solution for eco-friendly water purification. India, endowed with a rich diversity of microalgae and macroalgae, offers an abundant resource for such biotechnological applications. Due to their rapid growth, simple cultivation needs, and widespread availability, algae are particularly suitable for phycoremediation—the use of algae to remove or neutralize contaminants. Living algae, in contrast to non-living biomass, ensure a renewable and continuous supply of remediation material.

*This study investigates the phycoremediation potential of two locally available seaweeds, *Sargassum wightii* and *Gracilaria corticata*, in mitigating contamination caused by Servo Boat Engine Oil (20W40). Previous research has documented the accumulation of toxic substances in various macroalgae species, while certain green algae and diatoms have demonstrated the ability to metabolize polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs).*

Sudan dyes—particularly Sudan Black B—to visualize oil bioaccumulation in seaweed tissues. These staining techniques provide a valuable tool for documenting oil uptake and retention in bioremediated seaweeds, contributing to the understanding and validation of algae-based remediation strategies.

Keywords: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), sectioning, staining, Sudan Black B, Neutral red.

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1. Introduction

Phycoremediation is a natural, cost-effective method that uses the biological activity of algae to break down or neutralize harmful contaminants and their byproducts. It relies on biotech techniques that are generally well accepted by the public and can often be implemented directly at the contaminated site.

Algae have the natural ability to absorb pollutants from their aquatic environment. India possesses a rich diversity of both microalgae and macroalgae. Using algae as a raw material for water purification is highly advantageous due to their widespread presence and simple growth requirements. They can be cultivated easily and thrive in a variety of conditions.

A key advantage of using living algae over non-living biomass is their rapid growth rate, which ensures a continuous and renewable supply of material for removing pollutants. Numerous studies have shown that algae can accumulate toxic substances in their tissues when grown in contaminated waters. Notable examples include macroalgae such as *Ulva rigida* (Favero et al., 1996), *Padina gymnospora* (Karez et al., 1994), *Gracilaria tenuistipitata* (Hu et al., 1996), *Undaria pinnatifida* (Kim et al., 1999), *Cladophora* sp. (Sobhan et al., 1999), and *Cladophora glomerata* (McHardy et al., 1990).

Additionally, certain green algae and diatoms have demonstrated the ability to metabolize polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), particularly those with two or three aromatic rings (Warshawsky et al., 1995; Kirso and Irha, 1998; Lei et al., 2007).

The present study aimed to evaluate the phycoremediation potential of two locally available seaweeds, *Sargassum wightii* (Greville) and *Gracilaria corticata* (J. Agardh), in treating contamination caused by boat engine oil (Servo Boat Engine Oil 20W40). It is continuation of the earlier studies “Phycoremediation of hydrocarbon using two marine seaweeds from the Bay of Bengal coast of India” (Nisha et al., 2019).

The current investigation aimed to explore the application of fat-soluble dyes present in the tissues of oil-bioremediated seaweeds. Sudan dyes are commonly used to stain lipids, with

Sudan Black B being a slightly basic dye that binds to acidic groups in lipid compounds, allowing it to stain phospholipids as well.

Sudan Black B is also effective for staining neutral triglycerides, lipoproteins, and lipids in frozen sections or paraffin-embedded tissues. This makes it a valuable tool for documenting oil or lipid bioaccumulation in seaweed tissues, providing clear visual observation in microscopic sections. Neutral red staining studies were also extensively carried, recorded and explored in this study.

1.1 Objective

Histochemical analysis - Sectioning and staining of the seaweed before and after phycoremediation using Sudan Black stain.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Histochemical studies

2.1.1 Neutral red staining

After 80 days, portions of both oil-treated and untreated *Sargassum wightii* and *Gracilaria corticata* were freshly sectioned and stained with neutral red to detect the presence of lipids within the cells.

The phycoremediated seaweeds were collected from the conical flasks, and an appropriate amount of sample was fixed in FAA solution (Formalin: 5 ml, Acetic acid: 5 ml, 70% Ethyl alcohol: 90 ml). After 24 hours of fixation, the specimens were dehydrated using a graded series of tertiary-butyl alcohol, following the protocol described by Sass (1940). Infiltration was carried out by gradually adding paraffin wax (melting point 58–60°C) until the tertiary-butyl alcohol solution reached supersaturation. The specimens were then embedded in paraffin blocks for further analysis.

2.2 Sudan Black B staining method

The semithin sections were transferred to 70% alcohol and stained for 30 minutes at room temperature using a saturated solution of Sudan Black B in 70% alcohol. After staining, the sections were rinsed with water. The prepared specimens were then ready for photomicrography (Bronner 1975).

2.3 Photomicrographs

Ater the experiment period, the treated seaweed species were taken, careful sectioning was done. Percolation of the treated oil in the cells were observed and recorded by

photomicrographs. Photomicrographs were made from lower to higher magnifications using Nikonlab photo cameras under the microscope. The observations are explained using standard Anatomy books (Esau, 1964).

3. RESULTS

Histochemical studies on the semithin fixed thallus showed that the stain shows the amount of percolation of oil. The change in the morphology of cells due to the pollutant was noticed.

3.1 *Sargassum wightii*

25 ppm

- Deposition of oil in all the epidermal cells
- Meagre intrusion of oil particles in cortex - parenchymatous cells
- Mild plasmolysis occurred (Fig – 4b and 5a).

50 ppm

- Parenchyma cells in cortex showed noticeable oil deposition
- Parenchymatous cells appeared brown under bright field microscope
- Bleach out of green colour in chloroplasts within the cells (Fig – 4c and 5b).

75 ppm

- Observation of oil in the medullary cells.
- Plasmolysis and collapse of cells
- Oil globules and diffusion occurred in tissues (Fig – 4e and 5c).

100 ppm

- Cell wall becomes thin and disintegration started.
- Epidermal cells losses its shape and elongated.
- Flaccidity of epidermal cells
- Cortical cells were reduced in size leaving wavy layer (Fig – 4f and 5d).

3.2 *Gracilaria corticate*

100 ppm

- Slight oil deposition occurred in epidermal cells
- No oil intake in cortical cells (6b and 7a).

200 ppm

- Higher amount of oil deposition in epidermal cell
- Chloroplasts become undistinct
- Mild oil deposition in cortex (6c and 7b).

300 ppm.

- Oil particles observed in epidermis, sub epidermis and in few cortical cells
- Appearance of oil bodies inside the cells (6d and 7c).

400 ppm

- All the cells showed the presence of oil
- Oil deposition observed in cellular and inter cellular levels (6e and 7d).

500 ppm

- Epidermal cells were flaccid, original shape is lost
- Cells were elongated and turgid.
- Plasmolysis and collapsed cells were observed (6f and 7e).

Figure – 4

Histochemical analysis

Sargassum wightii stained with Sudan Black B

4a. Control

4b. 25 ppm

4c. 50 ppm

4d. Conceptacle at 50ppm

4e. 75 ppm

4f. 100 ppm

Figure – 5

Histochemical analysis

Sargassum wightii stained with Neutral red

5a. 25 ppm

5b. 50 ppm

5c. 75 ppm

5d. 100 ppm

Figure – 6

Histochemical analysis

Gracilaria corticata stained with Sudan Black B

6a. Control

6b. 100 ppm

6c. 200 ppm

6d. 300 ppm

6f. 400 ppm

6e. 500 ppm

Figure – 7

Histochemical analysis

Gracilaria corticata stained with Neutral red

7a. 100ppm

7b. 200 ppm

7c. 300 ppm

7d. 400 ppm

7e. 500 ppm

4. Discussion

Paraffin sections of the thalli stained with Sudan Black B revealed the presence of oil in nearly all cells across all tested concentrations in both seaweed species. At lower concentrations, some parenchymatous cortex cells showed oil deposition, while at higher concentrations, oil accumulated extensively in the epidermis, cortex, medulla, and even intercellular spaces. In *Sargassum wightii*, epidermal cells contained oil and became plasmolysed or collapsed under high concentrations.

Following the phycoremediation assay, *S. wightii* thalli appeared plasmolysed or collapsed. This may be due to oil content reducing blade desiccation, thereby allowing photosynthesis to continue—albeit at a diminished rate. Additionally, the weight of oil adhering to the kelp fronds may have caused them to break, primarily due to the presence of high molecular weight, water-insoluble hydrocarbons.

In contrast, *Gracilaria corticata* exhibited red pigment leaching. This suggests that oil may disrupt various stages of respiration, such as gas diffusion, glycolysis, and oxidative phosphorylation. While oil's mechanical interference with gas diffusion affects carbon dioxide more than oxygen (Schramm, 1972), its lipid solubility may cause pigment leaching, affecting seaweed coloration (O'Brien and Dixon, 1976).

5. Conclusion

Histochemical analysis of the seaweeds revealed that phycoremediated cells of *Sargassum wightii* exhibited plasmolysis under higher oil concentrations, indicating cellular damage. In contrast, *Gracilaria corticata* showed greater tolerance to the oil exposure. This observation was further supported by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images, which displayed surface smoothening and structural deformation in the brown seaweed (*S. wightii*).

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